

Pathologies and repair techniques of vaulted floors, the case of buildings in the Belcourt district, Algiers Algeria

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Abstract

Algeria has a rich and diverse architectural heritage that reflects its complex history and varied cultural influences. This heritage is visible throughout its cities, particularly in Algiers, known as “Algiers the White,” which showcases a blend of architectural influences. The city features Haussmannian-style buildings, Ottoman villas, and Neo-Moorish constructions, often merging styles to reflect different eras and civilizations. Among its districts, Belcourt is a significant example of Algiers' architectural evolution during the 19th and 20th centuries, characterized by its diverse architecture and modern infrastructure. Unfortunately, like much of Algeria's architectural and urban heritage, the constructions in this district face significant threats that compromise their preservation and integrity, with an alarming state of degradation observed in many buildings, highlighting the urgency for intervention to preserve this valuable heritage. In this context, our article aims to enhance and preserve this urban heritage through structural restoration, focusing particularly on floors, as they are most affected by degradation. We begin by identifying the various pathologies affecting them and then propose appropriate repair techniques. The study focuses on the specific challenges related to preserving these unique architectural structures, considering the available conditions and construction materials.

Keywords: *rehabilitation, vaulted floors, ancient constructions, floor pathologies.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Algerian architectural heritage is a valuable reflection of its history and cultural diversity. Protecting, enhancing, and rehabilitating these sites is essential to maintain national identity and sustain the housing stock, which supports economic stability. Despite efforts to maintain and protect these sites against various risks and time-related fluctuations, Algeria's rich heritage is in danger, with a large portion of historical buildings suffering from degradation due to neglect. In 2000, 431 monuments were listed as part of the national cultural heritage, but many more deserve protection. Recent efforts to raise awareness about rehabilitating old buildings have not been able to ensure effective protection against the threats facing these sites. Belcourt, a district in Algiers, exemplifies the challenge of preserving this heritage. This densely populated district reflects Algiers' urbanization history and is known for its French colonial architecture dating from the 19th and early 20th centuries. These constructions were adapted to European tastes while retaining some traditional Algerian elements. Notable historic buildings in this area include the Dey Hospital (built in the 19th century), the Officers' Pavilion (formerly an Ottoman house), the Tobacco Factory, Saint Augustine Church (representing Christian heritage in a Muslim-majority area), and Villa Abd-el-Tif (now a museum). In addition to these historic monuments, Belcourt, which has been urbanized over time, contains numerous residential buildings. These historic structures, representing not only the past but also the contemporary challenges of heritage conservation, suffer from various forms of degradation that sometimes lead to collapse, thus endangering human lives. The causes of this degradation include inadequate maintenance and care, unqualified “restorers,” uncontrolled urbanization, natural hazards (earthquakes, fires, landslides, and floods), atmospheric damage, and overuse or unauthorized modifications. These factors pose real threats to the stability of historic buildings and can lead to irreversible losses. The degradation of buildings has had a significant impact on the local population of this district, leading to an exodus of residents, with the population declining from 65,522 in 1987 to 44,050 in 2008. In response to this serious situation, it is urgent to implement a methodology aimed at finding appropriate solutions to repair the observed floor degradations (restoration remains possible) by thoroughly diagnosing the extent of the damage and then proposing effective repair, refurbishment, or reinforcement solutions. Our rehabilitation approach must include a campaign to raise public awareness about restoring their buildings, consulting specialists, and establishing a public policy in this regard.

II. SITE INFORMATION

A. Geographical Location

Belcourt (currently called Mohamed Belouizdad) is located about 3 kilometers southwest of the city center of Algiers, situated on a marshy plain at the foot of the Wild Woman's Ravine and the Bois des Arcades. This district is bordered to the south by the neighborhoods of La Redoute, Diar El Mahçoul, and El Hamma. It is crossed by Rue de Lyon (currently Rue Mohamed Belouizdad), which leads to the Ruisseau.

Figure 1 : Location of the Municipality of Belouizdad in the Wilaya of Algiers

B. Architectural Typology

The buildings in Belcourt primarily feature two modes of construction. First, continuous masonry construction, characterized by the use of load-bearing stone walls and bricks for the upper levels, with vaulted floor systems. Later, starting in the 1920s, reinforced concrete was introduced, allowing for greater flexibility in architectural design [17]. This analysis focuses on the first type of construction. The facades of these buildings often exhibit an eclectic style, integrating Haussmannian elements with rhythmic and symmetrical compositions. This includes regular openings, continuous balconies, and a horizontal hierarchy that distinguishes the base, the main body, and the crowning [18]. In terms of spatial organization, Belcourt's urban morphology is marked by rental apartment buildings. These structures, typical of colonial architecture, are generally 4 to 5 stories high and align along the main streets, adhering to strict urban planning rules set by the colonial administration [19].

Regarding interior spaces, colonial architecture often favored an introverted plan, with spaces organized around a central patio. This arrangement provided both privacy and a pleasant microclimate.

C. Construction Typology

To support our study, we selected a building suitable for restoration as a case study. This building shows structural pathologies, with the most severe issues affecting the floors, necessitating rehabilitation to restore its functionality. The building, constructed during the colonial era in the early 20th century, consists of six levels (a ground floor and five upper stories). It is primarily residential, with the ground floor used for commercial purposes and the upper floors for housing. The terraces are accessible.

The structural system of the building comprises a bracing system provided by load-bearing walls that are 60 cm thick. These walls are made of layers of dressed stone, squared rubble, or raw stones, joined exceptionally with a lime mortar bed [20,21].

The floors are vaulted floors, which appeared at the end of the 19th century as a replacement for wooden floors. In practice, there is a variety of metal-framed floors with a nearly identical load-bearing structure. This structure consists of metal profiles (joists) spaced 40 to 60 cm apart, filled with solid bricks (or sometimes hollow bricks) known as "vaulted" (Figure 2), giving a vaulted effect. In some cases, the bricks are laid flat.

Once the framework is in place, a layer of rammed earth mixed with sand and lime is added. The finishing layer consists of sand and lime, sometimes topped with a tile or fired brick finish. The underside of the floor is covered with a false ceiling, made up of elements such as wall plates, ties, reed lathes, and a mix of lime and plaster mortar.

Figure 2 : Vaulted floor with solid bricks

The vertical circulation is provided by a balanced staircase. As for the foundations, they are strip foundations.

D. Materials and Construction Techniques

The colonial-era buildings in Belcourt, influenced by European models, are notable for the introduction of new methods and materials, such as:

1. **Cut Stone:** Imported from southern France, it symbolized prestige and durability.
2. **Masonry in Stone and Brick:** Buildings were often constructed with continuous masonry, featuring load-bearing walls made of stone for lower levels and brick for upper levels. This system was complemented by vaulted floors supported by metal beams, a technique that evolved to reinforced concrete from the 1920s onward [22] [3].
3. **Iron:** Used in metal structures, especially for balconies and verandas, allowing for decorative elements while reinforcing the structure [3].
4. **Ceramic Tiles:** Frequently used for flooring and roofing, adding a colorful and local touch to the constructions [23].

E. Construction Techniques:

The techniques employed were often influenced by local architecture while incorporating European styles. The buildings were generally designed around interior spaces such as patios, promoting natural air circulation and optimized lighting. This approach allowed adaptation to Algiers' climatic conditions while meeting the functional needs of residents. In summary, colonial architecture in Belcourt demonstrates a hybridization of traditional materials and modern techniques, reflecting the aspirations and challenges of the colonial era in Algeria.

III. PATHOLOGIES AND REPAIR TECHNIQUES FOR VAULTED FLOORS

A. Pathologies

The following outlines the main issues observed in the vaulted floors:

- Moisture in the Floor (Figure 3).
- Damage and Corrosion of Metal Beams, sometimes leading to partial or total collapse of the floor, along with the destruction of the finish layer, often exacerbated by ambient humidity (Figure 4).
- Visible Rust Stains, caused by oxidation of the beams (Figure 5).
- Detachment of the False Ceiling from the rest of the floor.
- Degradation of Bricks and Mortar, caused by salt crystallization and structural movements, resulting in cracking, crumbling, and loss of cohesion.
- Waterproofing Issues, caused by aging materials, lack of maintenance, and structural movements.
- Cracks Formation, frequently observed at joints and angles of the structures, caused by ground movements or thermal variations.
- Deformation of Beams, particularly creep due to the weight of the floors, is another significant pathology.

Figure 3: Presence of moisture in the ceiling (author)

Figure 4: Collapse of the floor with cracking and lifting of the covering (author).

Figure 5 :Corrosion of metal joists (author).

B. Repair Techniques

The intervention depends on the degree of degradation for each situation. The following approaches are proposed:

B1. Restoration of Bricks and Mortar: This part can be summarized as follows:

1. Repointing with compatible mortar (lime-based).
2. Replacing damaged bricks.
3. Grouting to consolidate the masonry.

B2. Improving Waterproofing:

1. Application of breathable waterproof coatings.
2. Installation of drainage systems.
3. Treatment of critical points (wall-to-floor junctions).

B3. Crack Repair:

Epoxy resin injection can be used to treat structural cracks, thus reinforcing the integrity of the repaired element.

B4. Reinforcement of Joists:

When the joists show minor degradation without leading to floor collapse, they can be reinforced.

This involves applying an anti-corrosion treatment to extend their lifespan, followed by the addition of tie rods or composite materials to restore their load-bearing capacity [4] [5].

B5. Restoration of Coverings:

Damaged coverings should be carefully restored or replaced to prevent water infiltration and enhance the building's aesthetics.

B6. Replacement Technique with a New Metal Floor:

When the metal joists are severely corroded, causing the floor to collapse (as shown in Figure 4), a replacement with a new floor is recommended. This involves using a composite floor system (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Composite Floor.

To construct the new floor, the following steps were carried out:

1. Removing the Tiling:

Remove the floor tiles using a hydraulic or electric chisel with moderate power. The use of heavy tools is prohibited to avoid weakening the structure (Figure 7).

2. Cutting the Metal Joists

Cut the metal joists using an electric grinder (Figure 8).

3. Repairing Spalls and Cracks in Load-Bearing Walls Repair spalls and cracks in the load-bearing walls and coat them with properly dosed cement mortar. If necessary, use galvanized mesh (potholes) at areas with significant coating overload. This operation should be carried out in at least two phases.

4. Incorporating New Joists (IPE 80):

Insert the new IPE 80 joists into the load-bearing walls with a spacing of 60 cm. Ensure their proper sealing (Figure 9).

5. Installing the Metal Profile:

Place the metal profile, such as TR35, on the IPE 80 joists (Figure 10).

6. Providing Connectors: Install connectors fixed to the purlins by welding to ensure the concrete effectively collaborates with the metal structure (Figure 10).

7. Pouring the Concrete Slab:

Concret a 15 cm-thick concrete slab mixed at 350 kg/m³ with CPJ 42.5 cement. This slab should be reinforced with welded mesh of 150x150x5 mm (Figure 11).

After completing these steps, proceed to repair the cracked false ceilings. If the lath condition is good, simply seal the cracks with plaster. Otherwise, replace damaged lath sections or secure them if they are merely detached.

Figure 7 :Removal of tiling (author)

Figure 8 :cutting of metal joists (author).

Figure 9 :Installation of the new joists (author).

Figure 10 :Installation of the metal profile and welded mesh on the joists (author)

Figure 11 :Pouring of a concrete screed (author)

Conclusion

The preservation of vaulted floors in Belcourt buildings represents a significant technical and heritage challenge. A multidisciplinary approach, combining expertise in structural engineering, knowledge of traditional materials, and sensitivity to historical value, is essential to ensure the longevity of these unique structures. Repair techniques must be tailored to each specific case, taking into account the observed issues and the constraints associated with preserving Algeria's architectural heritage.

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